

Reception and willingness to share pseudo-profound bullshit and their relation to other epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive ability in Slovakia and Romania

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ABSTRACT

A recent study (Pennycook et al., 2015) found that the propensity to judge randomly generated, syntactically correct (i.e., bullshit) statements as profound was associated with a variety of conceptually relevant variables (e.g., intuitive cognitive style, supernatural beliefs). Besides generalizing these findings to a different cultural setting, we examined the relationships to sharing the bullshit on social media. Rating nonsense as profound was associated with a lower cognitive ability; a stronger belief in the paranormal, alternative medicine, and conspiracies; and ontological confusion. The more profound a statement was rated to be, the more likely it was to be shared; and propensity for sharing bullshit was predicted by ontological confusion and religious beliefs. Bullshit receptivity and sharing may be closely related to several dimensions of epistemically suspect beliefs; people with these propensities are relatively open to vague statements resembling New Age spirituality.

Keywords: bullshit, analytic thinking, supernatural beliefs, conspiratorial ideation, complementary and alternative medicine.

Introduction

Bullshit, defined as either useless talk (Barnum, 1866; Postman, 1969), nonsense (Black, 1982), or as statements produced without concern for the truth (Frankfurt, 2005), has long been a topic of interest among linguists and philosophers (Black, 1982; Frankfurt, 2005; Postman, 1969), yet it has only recently attracted the attention of psychologists (Pennycook, Cheyne, Barr, Koehler, & Fugelsang, 2015). One of the defining features of pseudo-profound bullshit according to Pennycook et al. (2015) is that “it attempts to impress rather than to inform; to be engaging rather than instructive” (p. 550). It uses buzzwords and deliberate vagueness to mask the lack of meaning. Vagueness is deliberately used to obscure the meaning of the statement and hence convey the impression of “deep meaning” (i.e., profundity). What is considered profound or deeply meaningful may differ across individuals. Pennycook et al. (2015) had participants judge the profundity of randomly generated statements (i.e., how deeply meaningful they are), thus ensuring there was no intended meaning. In this way, these truly nonsensical, but syntactically correct, sentences can be viewed as instances of bullshit according to Frankfurt’s definition (2005), that is, statements where there is no concern for the truth, merely an aim to impress (through the use of New Age buzzwords). Importantly, Pennycook et al. (2015) found that the propensity to judge these statements as profound was associated with a variety of conceptually relevant variables (e.g., intuitive cognitive style, supernatural beliefs). They were also associated with a preference for conservative presidential candidates in US elections (Pfattheicher & Schindler, 2016) and for a free market economy (Sterling, Jost, & Pennycook, 2016). In a more recent study, Pennycook and Rand (2017) examined willingness to share fake news in conjunction with bullshit reception, and they found higher bullshit receptivity was positively related to a greater willingness to share fake news (and news in general). Fake news can be understood as stories fabricated without regard for the truth and with the goal of being circulated widely and rapidly on the internet, which makes them, according to Frankfurt’s definition (2005), similar to bullshit or actual cases of bullshit. Although fake news can be regarded as a form of bullshit, it differs from pseudo-transcendental bullshit as measured by the Bullshit Receptivity Scale. Pennycook and Rand did not examine the sharing of pseudo-transcendental bullshit in their study.

Although the phenomenon of bullshit is not restricted to Western developed countries, all the existing research examining bullshit receptivity has used North American samples, which raises the question of whether the findings are generalizable to non-North American samples. Indeed, post-communist Eastern European countries like Slovakia and Romania can differ from North American or Western European countries in many important aspects of openness to bullshit. For example, their more traditional form of Christianity (Pollack, 2003) may make people more suspicious of transcendental New Age ideas and therefore reduce receptivity of pseudo-profound bullshit. It is important to examine possible cross-cultural differences in the reception of pseudo-profound bullshit and to generalize to other samples the findings on the relation of bullshit receptivity to other cognitively relevant variables, because this will corroborate the validity and reliability of the psychological findings (Henrich, Heine, & Norenzayan, 2010). Moreover, it is theoretically important to examine whether general openness to bullshit and other epistemically suspect beliefs is related to the same individual predictors because this could lead to more universal interventions against the spread of bullshit. Therefore, it is important to examine whether people are willing to share this kind of pseudo-profound bullshit. For one thing, it could tell us that they consider some bullshit statements to be profound; for another, it may provide us with an insight into why people mindlessly share content that has no informative value.

What constitutes bullshit?

There is no single agreed upon definition of the term bullshit, with many scholars using different terms to refer to similar concepts. Postman (1969) described bullshit as pointless talk. He then described a bullshit taxonomy containing four categories. *Pomposity* is characterized by the use of fancy titles, terms, and sentences designed to obscure the bullshitter's insufficiencies and make listeners question themselves. The second category is *fanaticism*, and the two most dangerous types are bigotry and Eichmannism (i.e., intolerance of any data not confirming the bullshitter's point of view). *Inanity* is the third category, defined as "ignorance presented in the cloak of sincerity" (p. 2). The rise in its use was credited to the development of the mass media, which has provided both the channel and the audience for unsolicited opinions that make no real contribution to public debates – as

noted by Barr (2015) who considers the current era to be one not only of information, but also of misinformation: “the age of Bullshit” (p. 1). The final category is *superstition*: the authoritative expression of a belief not supported by factual or scientific evidence, styled as “ignorance presented in the cloak of authority” (p. 2). Frankfurt's (2005) significantly more popular *On Bullshit* attempted to correct the lack of a bullshit theory by considering dictionary definitions, comparing bullshit and humbug (a term which arguably describes the same concept, albeit more politely and with less intensity, and used by Barnum, 1866; Black, 1982), and providing various practical examples. He concluded that the essence of bullshit lies in the “lack of connection to a concern with the truth” (p. 8), and that it “is not that it is false but that it is phony” (p. 12). The bullshitter has no concern for the accuracy of what is being transmitted as long as the desired effect is obtained (e.g., to impress, to gain advantage, to get out of a particular situation). Buekens and Boundry (2015) distinguished between obscurantism and bullshit, claiming that while the bullshitter is uninterested in both the language employed and the audience's reception, obscurantism is an attempt to mask the lack of depth and insight using elaborate linguistic formulations that suggest the need for further, more comprehensive investigation. Moreover, obscurantism specifically aims to keep the audience perpetually trapped in a futile search for deeper understanding, whilst maintaining the speaker's more desirable, knowledgeable image.

More recently, Meibauer (2016) has added a third aspect to the definition of bullshit, drawing on Frankfurt's definition, namely that there is a loose concern for the truth and that attempts are made to obscure this fact from the listener, and the bullshitter therefore expresses more certainty than the issue requires. Wakeham (2017) argued that bullshit is not just a general epistemological problem, but specifically concerns social epistemology, that is, how we acquire knowledge through social resources and the problematic nature of second-hand sources. He drew on research showing that people generally believe that their interaction partners are honest, particularly those close to them, and that social familiarity lowers epistemic vigilance (Bond & DePaulo, 2006).

Pseudo-profound bullshit, empirically investigated by Pennycook et al. (2015), has the added attribute of being intentionally vague so as to inspire profoundness and a sense of “deep meaning”. Consistent with the definition of obscurantism, its goal is to impress and not to inform. In contrast to

previous philosophical work (Black, 1982; Frankfurt, 2005; Postman, 1969) on bullshitters and their intentions, Pennycook et al. (2015) focused their attention on the bullshittee¹ and examined general receptivity to bullshit and differences within that. They proposed two mechanisms to explain how “general” bullshit receptivity works: (1) bullshit receptivity – a greater initial expectance of deeper meaning or profundity (a high response bias towards accepting something as true), and (2) bullshit detection (i.e. bullshit sensitivity) – the failure or otherwise to realize the need to subject the information to scepticism or deliberate reasoning (a failure in conflict monitoring – De Neys, 2014). People more sensitive to bullshit should be better able to distinguish between truly (or conventionally) profound statements and vaguely formulated nonsense statements. In other words, they are less impressed by the vagueness of pseudo-profound bullshit. The Bullshit Receptivity Scale designed by Pennycook and colleagues, contains twenty randomly generated syntactically correct sentences (e.g., “Wholeness quiets infinite phenomena”), formed by combining buzzwords extracted from Tweets sent by Deepak Chopra² with ten of his Tweets (e.g., “Attention and intention are the mechanics of manifestation”).

The results showed negative correlations between bullshit receptivity and variables such as cognitive ability, verbal intelligence, and analytic thinking, while positive correlations were observed between bullshit receptivity, ontological confusion, and epistemically suspect beliefs.

Problems with the empirical examination of bullshit

This novel approach to investigating bullshit receptivity is not without critics though. Dalton (2016) doubted whether the items designed by Pennycook et al. (2015) can be classified as bullshit. This is because the sentences are considered to be bullshit on the grounds that they have been

¹ This propensity to share bullshit deemed profound by bullshittees (people receiving bullshit from bullshitters) should be considered distinct from the propensity of bullshitters to share or spread it to their “victims”. The bullshitter’s goal is to manipulate people into believing bullshit by obscuring its shallowness with impressive language, while the bullshittee sincerely believes that the bullshit has a profound meaning that might be worth sharing with others.

² Deepak Chopra is an Indian-born American author, public speaker, alternative medicine advocate, and a prominent figure in the New Age movement, criticized for his misuse of scientific terminology and "nonsensical references to quantum physics" (Kaminer, 2008, p. 92).

randomly generated. Dalton argued that their subjective impact on the participant is not taken into consideration. If a sentence is considered to be insightful and wise, can it be labelled bullshit? Stating that “beauty, like bullshit, may be in the eyes of the beholder”, Dalton (2016, p. 2) questioned whether Frankfurt’s (2005) definition of bullshit can be applied to sentences that may exhibit profundity and suggested, based on radical reader-response theory, that meaning is constructed by readers solely and that random phenomena can help create meaning when considerable time and contemplative effort are invested in the process. While this criticism raised some interesting points for further research, such as how exactly bullshit statements are perceived when they are attributed high profundity ratings, the debate is mainly a conceptual one. It has been rebutted by Pennycook et al. (2016) on the grounds that if the bullshit is defined as a statement produced without concern for the truth, then random-generated statements fulfil this definition. Moreover, they suggested that Dalton was probably focusing on a nonessential aspect of bullshit, because “it is not the understanding of the recipient of bullshit that makes something bullshit, it is the lack of concern (and perhaps even understanding) of the truth or meaning of statements by the one who utters it” (p.125). So even if profundity or meaning can be seen in the randomly generated sentences, they are still consistent with Frankfurt’s definition of bullshit (that focuses on the producer of the bullshit rather than the receiver), which is used by Pennycook et al. (2015). Moreover, it enables us to distinguish between people who are more receptive to bullshit statements and those who are not.

Sharing bullshit

According to statista.com, in 2017, 71 percent of internet users were social network users and it is expected that this percentage will grow. Sharing information has never been easier and people usually share information to entertain, educate, inspire, or convince others. However, besides the overwhelming amount of informative content, there is a growing number of pointless (at best) and manipulative (at worst) content, which makes the ability to distinguish between real information and

pointless bullshit even more important³. Sharing unfounded and untruthful content poses dangers to society, partly because people have a more relaxed attitude towards it than they do to lying, and partly because, when successful, it reinforces a distancing from investigating the truth, progressively leading to the person becoming completely uninterested in it (Frankfurt, 2005). Nonetheless, social media is just a tool that can be used for both prosocial purposes and to pursue a hidden political agenda. Therefore, it is important to study whether people are able to distinguish nonsense from fact-related statements.

In their recent study, Pennycook and Rand (2017) made an explicit connection between bullshit and fake news: “One might refer to fake news as a type of bullshit, as fake news stories are constructed with a disregard for the truth (in keeping with the definition of bullshit put forth by Frankfurt, 2005).” (p.7). The difference between fake news and bullshit is that fake news is not the pseudo-profound variety of bullshit. Pennycook and Rand explored whether the ability to detect bullshit correlates with the ability to detect fake news and they found that receptivity to pseudo-profound bullshit positively predicted the perceived accuracy of fake news – an association that was partially mediated by cognitive reflection. Although their main aim was to examine how receptivity to fake news is linked to political partisanship, in Study 2 they asked the participants to indicate how willing they would be to share the news (faked and real) on social networks. They found that receptivity to pseudo-profound bullshit was related to higher perceived accuracy of fake news, but not to higher perceived accuracy of real news, and that people more receptive to bullshit were more likely to share both real and fake news. However, because sharing real news on social media was negatively associated with analytic thinking, they concluded that “at least for real news stories, perceptions of accuracy and social media sharing are not two versions of the same judgment” (Pennycook & Rand,

³ As Lewandowsky, Ecker, and Cook (2017) argued, we are not so far from a dystopian world in which knowledge is considered “elitist” and in which important issues are decided on the opinion markets of Twitter or Facebook. In such a world, power lies with the most influential on social media, who can spread information quickly and create the illusion of widespread opinion. The important role of social media was evident during the 2016 US presidential campaign – not only did the independent fact checker *PolitiFact* judge 70 percent of all Donald Trump’s statements to be false or misleading, but the impression of his popularity may have been boosted by Twitter bots spreading the lies (Lewandowsky et al., 2017).

2017, p. 38). Therefore, they speculated that the decision to share news articles on social media is not driven primarily by belief in their accuracy, but rather by concerns about reputation or virtue signalling (Bazarova, Taft, Choi, & Cosley, 2013).

In our study, in contrast to Pennycook and Rand's, we did not focus on the relationship between receptivity to pseudo-profound bullshit and accuracy perception and sharing fake news, but on the willingness to share pseudo-profound bullshit. We expected the sharing bullshit measure to provide us with an additional indirect measure of bullshit receptivity, because people unconcerned with the truth and wanting to impress others should be less likely to closely examine these statements than more analytically thinking people would. Moreover, it is still unclear whether the connection between openness to pseudo-profound bullshit and openness to other unfounded beliefs extends to other cultures. Therefore, in the next section we discuss whether some kinds of bullshit can be perceived as universal and then elaborate more on the motivation of our study.

Is bullshit universal?

Psychologists began studying bullshit following the seminal work of Pennycook and colleagues in 2015, but all the research so far has relied upon North America samples. It remains unclear whether receptivity and willingness to share bullshit extend to non-North American cultures. Henrich, Heine, and Norenzayan (2010) stated that most psychological studies use samples of college psychology students, who differ not only from people from less developed countries, but even from less educated people in the same country. Replicating results using samples from a different cultural background is therefore important.

There are two main reasons for wondering whether our samples from Slovakia and Romania will show the same level of receptivity to transcendental bullshit as was found in the North American sample used in the original study.

First, there are cultural differences related to psychological characteristics, as highlighted by Henrich et al. (2010) and others (Deppe et al., 2015; Talhelm et al., 2015), as well as differences related to historical experience of authoritarian regimes. For example, research on unsubstantiated

beliefs (supernatural beliefs, conspiracy theories, pseudoscientific claims) shows that despite similar findings (i.e., correlations between various unsubstantiated beliefs or with intuitive thinking), the substance of the beliefs may differ (Brotherton, French, & Pickering, 2013). Ballová Mikušková (2017) pointed out that some items from the generic conspiracy measure can pose problems for researchers in post-communist countries because agreeing with items such as “Government agencies secretly keep certain outspoken celebrities and citizens under constant surveillance” or “There are ongoing, hidden efforts to marginalize, control, or destroy certain groups of people through the use of political policies” does not necessarily indicate a conspiracy mentality, as such statements were (and sometimes still are) true in these countries. Similarly, in a cross-cultural comparison of generic conspiracy mentality across cultures, a higher conspiracy mentality was found in Turkey than among Europeans and North Americans (Bruder, Haffke, Neave, Nouripanah, & Imhoff, 2013). Agreeing with items such as “I think that government agencies closely monitor all citizens” does not reveal the same level of suspicion in more authoritarian regimes as it does in Western countries with a long tradition of democracy.

Second, Pennycook et al. (2015) examined a specific type of bullshit – transcendental pseudo-profound bullshit – which largely taps into New Age spirituality (or at least its vocabulary) and is used by the guru figure Deepak Chopra. However, Eastern European countries (usually also post-communist) differ from North America countries (or even Western European countries) in their religiosity. Pollack (2003) reported that traditional religion is losing its significance and new, less institutionalized, forms of religions are emerging in modern Western societies, but Eastern European countries experienced a revival of traditional Christianity following the collapse of the communist regimes. A majority of Slovaks and Romanians belong to the Catholic Church, which is one of the most traditional Christian churches. According to polls conducted in 2002, 72 percent of Slovaks and 96 percent of Romanians belonged to a church, moreover 77 percent of Slovaks and 98 percent of Romanians believed in God. Other differences were observed in so-called “new” and “old” forms of religiousness outside the church. New Age spirituality and Zen meditation are examples of new forms, and astrology, faith healing, and witchcraft are examples of old forms.

In countries like Albania, Hungary, Poland, Romania, and Slovakia, in which percentages of people with traditional belief systems are high, older forms of religiousness like astrology or belief in faith healers are more broadly accepted. In more secularized countries like the Czech Republic, Estonia, East Germany or Slovenia the number of people believing in the effects of Zen meditation is higher than the number of people believing in astrology or faith healers. (Pollack, 2003, p. 327)

Moreover, only a small proportion of the population reported believing in the message of New Age cults: 2.2 percent in Romania and 3.2 percent in Slovakia. Knowledge of New Age spirituality was not common; levels of religious diversity are generally low in post-communist countries and mainly reflect pre-communist patterns (Sarkissian, 2009). On the other hand, familiarity with New Age beliefs seems to be more common among participants from the original study, which was reflected in answers to a control question asking participants whether they knew of Deepak Chopra and in every study between 42 percent and 54 percent of participants admitted they did.

Aim of the paper

As we have argued above, epistemically suspect beliefs contain culturally specific elements, so it is important to establish whether bullshit receptivity can be generalized using the original items of the Bullshit Receptivity Scale adapted for other languages. We chose to study Slovakia and Romania mainly because of accessibility and affordability. The two countries share a communist past, but their cultures differ. The results by Pennycook et al. (2015) suggest that the first, and currently only, empirical measure of bullshit is methodologically adequate; nevertheless, it is necessary to verify whether it is generalizable to different cultures and samples (Henrich et al., 2010). Therefore our main aim is to examine whether we can observe the same patterns of relationships between receptivity and sensitivity to bullshit and other conceptually relevant variables in a culturally different sample from the one used by Pennycook et al. (2015). To do so, we selected materials which measured the same

variables as those in the study by Pennycook et al. (2015). We included a novel variable that enabled us to examine not only whether people are receptive to pseudo-profound bullshit but also whether they are inclined to share it on social networks. This was so we could test whether those who share quotes are a distinct population with significantly different levels of epistemically suspect beliefs.

Our main research question was whether our sample would be less receptive to pseudo-profound bullshit than the sample in the study by Pennycook et al. (2015), and whether receptivity to pseudo-profound bullshit would generally show positive relationships with epistemically suspect beliefs and negative relationships with measures of cognitive abilities and reflective cognitive style. Our secondary goal was to explore whether we would obtain the same results for willingness to share pseudo-profound bullshit.

Methods

Participants

We used convenience sampling to obtain our samples. The Slovak ($n = 76$) and Romanian ($n = 45$) participants completed several measures of bullshit receptivity, willingness to share pseudo-profound bullshit, cognitive abilities, and thinking dispositions. The Slovak sample consisted predominately of female (98.7% women, $M_{age} = 23.38$ years) undergraduate students taking various pedagogy programs, who participated in the survey in return for extra credits as part of their psychology course. The Romanian sample had a more equal gender balance and was younger (60% male, $M_{age} = 19.36$ years). It consisted of one sample comprising 11th and 12th graders (the penultimate and highest grades in the Romanian school system) from a top secondary school in the city of Oradea and a second sample that was recruited via posts on university social network sites. The data from the Slovak and Romanian participants were combined for the present research. The final sample consisted of 121 participants (77% female, $M_{age} = 21.9$, $SD_{age} = 6.54$) who completed an online survey.

Materials⁴

Bullshit receptivity was assessed using the three scales from the second study by Pennycook et al. (2015): the 30-item *Bullshit Receptivity Scale (BRS)* composed of 20 randomly generated sentences (e.g. “Hidden meaning transforms unparalleled abstract beauty.” or “Wholeness quiets infinite phenomena.”) and 10 of Deepak Chopra’s Tweets (e.g. “Attention and intention are the mechanics of manifestation.”); we decided to include whole Tweets in the scale after we observed that the two measures were strongly correlated ($r = .88$). The internal consistency of the resulting scale was excellent ($\alpha = .96$). We also included two other measures from the original study: the 10-item *Mundane Statements Scale (MSS)* containing meaningful but trivial sentences (e.g., “Newborn babies require constant attention.”); and the 10-item *Motivational Quotes Scale (MQS)* (e.g., “A wet person does not fear the rain.”). The MSS was used to assess whether a person has a general response bias and considers even mundane statements to be profound, while the MQS was used to evaluate the ability to detect bullshit, by making participants produce different ratings of sentences that are generally considered to be profound and randomly generated sentences. All the items were rated on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (not at all profound) to 5 (very profound). Each scale had a different number of items so the mean scores were computed. The mean score for the BRS indicated level of *bullshit receptivity* – the general tendency to judge bullshit statements as profound, while the *bullshit sensitivity* was measured by subtracting mean BSR ratings from the mean MQS scores to indicate the degree to which people distinguish between truly (conventionally) profound wisdoms and randomly generated bullshit.

In addition to the materials originally used by Pennycook et al. (2015), we asked participants to indicate the probability of them sharing each of the statements on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (very unlikely) to 5 (very likely). We calculated the mean sharing scores separately for the statements on the Bullshit Receptivity Scale, Mundane Statements Scale, and Motivational Quotes Scale.

⁴ All the materials were translated from English into the language of the participants by native speakers. They were not pretested for comprehension. All the materials are available at osf.io/yn7c6 in English, Romanian, and Slovak.

Analytic thinking was measured using the expanded 7-item *Cognitive Reflection Test* (CRT; Toplak, West, & Stanovich, 2014). The CRT is a simple test for measuring how well a person tends to process things (or for measuring cognitive impulsiveness/laziness in defaulting to the autonomous mind) and ability to postpone judgement (cognitive reflection). It is a simple test of a single type of cognitive ability that predicts some preferences so well that it is an effective reflection of cognitive ability (Frederick, 2005). The same scoring was used: correct responses were ascribed 1 point.

Cognitive abilities were measured by the *Vienna Matrix Test* (VMT; Klose, Černochová, & Král, 2002). The VMT is time-limited, consists of 24 items of increasing difficulty, and is based on the classic Raven's test of progressive matrices. The test is supposed to be culture neutral, because it does not rely on verbal content. Each task contains a 3x3 picture matrix with a picture missing in the third row. The participant has to correctly complete the series using one of eight possibilities. The VMT shows strong correlations with the Intelligence Structure Test ($r = .85$, $N = 115$) and with Raven's matrices ($r = .92$, $N = 120$) (Klose, et al., 2002). Klose et al. (2002) concluded that it is a reliable indication of the general cognitive factor.

Epistemically suspect beliefs were measured using several questionnaires: the Ontological Confusion Scale, Santa Clara Strength of Religious Faith Questionnaire, Paranormal Belief Scale, Belief in Complementary and Alternative Medicine, and the Generic Conspiracist Beliefs scale, which we describe below in more detail.

The *Ontological Confusion Scale* (Lindeman & Aarnio, 2007) comprises 31 statements containing mentalizing matter (e.g., Old furniture knows things about the past.), physicalizing mental (e.g., An unstable human mind is disintegrating.) or biologizing mental (e.g., An evil thought is contaminated.). For comparison, there were four entirely metaphorical statements (e.g., A wailing wind is a flute.) and four true statements (e.g., Running water is fluid.). The participants rated the items on a scale ranging from 1 (only metaphorically true) to 5 (only literally true). A higher score indicates a higher level of ontological confusion (i.e., mistakenly attributing a literal meaning to metaphorical statements).

The *Santa Clara Strength of Religious Faith Questionnaire* (Plante, 2010) is a short 10-item self-report measure assessing the strength of religious faith and engagement. It does not relate to a specific

religion. Participants indicate their agreement with statements such as “I pray daily” on a scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree), thus a higher score indicated stronger religious faith.

Paranormal Belief (Tobacyk, 2004) is a 26-item self-reported scale which gives a measure of the degree of belief in each of seven dimensions: Traditional Religious Belief, Psi, Witchcraft, Superstition, Spiritualism, Extraordinary Life Forms, and Precognition. Participants indicate their agreement with statements such as “Black magic really exists” on a scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). A higher score indicates a stronger belief in the paranormal. We also analysed whether the items loaded onto seven proposed factors: Traditional Religious Belief, Psi, Witchcraft, Superstition, Spiritualism, Extraordinary Life Forms, and Precognition (Tobacyk, 2004). The results of the inspection of the scree plot revealed one strong factor explaining 30.46 percent of total variance, with two smaller factors each explaining 11.01 percent and 8.36 percent. Therefore, we decided to eliminate all the items with factor loadings of less than 0.5, and we were left with 16 items⁵. This one factor now explained 42.99 percent of total variance.

Belief in Complementary and Alternative Medicine and frequency of use (Lindeman, 2011). The participants were asked whether they believed 12 alternative treatments to be effective (Oriental medicine; Yoga, relaxation or meditation for treating illnesses; Homeopathy; Energy healing; Megadose vitamin and micronutrient therapy; Aromatherapy; Naturopathy, such as herbal therapy or stone therapy; Life force and spiritual energy healing, such as Reiki; treatments based on the four elements of the human body (earth, water, fire, and air), such as Ayurveda; Spiritual healing; and Distance healing). They indicated their answers on a scale from 1 (do not believe at all) to 5 (believe fully); 0 = cannot say. After responding to these questions, the participants were again presented with all 12 alternative treatments and asked: “How often have you used the above-mentioned treatments?” The alternatives were 1 = never, 2 = once, 3 = two or three times, 4 = few times, 5 = monthly, 6 = weekly, and 7 = daily. Two scores were calculated – Belief in Complementary and Alternative Medicine (BCAM) and Use of Complementary and Alternative Medicine (UCAM).

⁵ The items relating to Traditional Religious Belief (with one exception), Superstition, and Extraordinary Life Forms (with one exception) were eliminated.

The *Generic Conspiracist Beliefs scale* (Brotherton et al., 2013) is a 15-item scale with three items representing each of these five factors: government malfeasance, extraterrestrial cover-up, malevolent global conspiracies, personal wellbeing, and control of information. Participants indicated the extent to which they agreed with the items on a scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree); thus a higher score revealed a higher prevalence of conspiracy beliefs. Only two distinct factors emerged from the factor analysis verifying the five factors: a general conspiracy ideation factor explaining 46.67 percent of total variance and a factor where UFO related items explained 12.53 percent of total variance.

Procedure

After filling in the short demographic questionnaire (gender, age, highest level of education), the participants completed the tasks in the following order: bullshit receptivity, ontological confusion, cognitive reflection, bullshit sharing, scientific reasoning (not reported here), strength of religious beliefs, paranormal belief scale, conspiracy ideation, belief in alternative medicine, use of alternative medicine, attention check question⁶, cognitive abilities test, and a few control questions at the end of the survey. The whole procedure took about an hour and participants either received an extra credit for their participation in the study (Slovak sample) or could enter a lottery as a small financial incentive (ten €20 vouchers could be won by the Romanian sample).

Results

The basic descriptive data pertaining to all the materials and internal scale consistency can be found in Table 1. As expected, the motivational quotes were rated as significantly more profound than

⁶ An attention check question was included before the intelligence test was taken. The instructions read: “Recent research in decision-making has shown that decision-making is affected by the context in which the decision takes place. Differences in how people feel, their prior experience and knowledge – all affect the decisions they make. To better understand how people make decisions, we are interested in several questions about you. In this case we are interested in whether you read all the instructions carefully; because if not, some of the results may be invalid. To show that you have read these instructions, please ignore the next question about how you feel and instead give as your answer the option ‘none of the above’.” This was followed by a question about how the participants felt at that moment and the required answer was “none of the above”.

the bullshit statements ($t(120) = 13.491, p < .001, d = 1.23$), which in turn were rated more profound than the mundane statements ($t(120) = 1.989, p = .049, d = 0.18$). Willingness to share the bullshit, motivational, and mundane statements rating was lower in all cases than their profundity ratings (all $ps < .05, ds > 0.20$). The majority of statements were rated mid-way between not at all profound and very profound, as in Pennycook et al.'s study (2015).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for all the materials used in the study

	<i>M</i>	<i>Mdn</i>	<i>SD</i>	Items	<i>α</i>
BSR	2.87	2.97	0.63	30	.92
MSS	2.63	2.10	1.36	10	.96
MQS	3.87	4.00	0.71	10	.80
SBS	1.88	1.70	0.76	30	.96
SMQ	3.41	3.70	1.07	10	.90
SMS	2.39	2.20	1.20	10	.94
CRT	3.35	3.00	2.27	7	.77
VMT	17.12	18.00	4.53	24	.84
BCAM	1.96	1.91	0.83	11	.79
UCAM	1.54	1.45	0.52	11	.65
GCBS	2.98	2.93	0.87	15	.92
GCBS-G	3.16	3.25	0.92	12	.92
GCBS-UFO	2.28	2.00	1.15	3	.87
OC	2.50	2.55	0.61	31	.89
OC-metaphor	2.27	2.25	0.86	4	.47
OC-literal	4.22	4.25	0.74	4	.54
PBS	2.40	2.31	0.81	16	.91
RB	2.30	2.40	0.88	10	.95

Notes. $N = 121$. BSR = bullshit receptivity, MQS = motivational quotes receptivity, MSS = mundane statement receptivity, SBS = sharing bullshit, SMQ = sharing motivational quotes, SMS = sharing mundane statements, CRT = cognitive reflection test, VMT = Vienna matrix test, BCAM = belief in complementary and alternative medicine, UCAM = use of complementary and alternative medicine, GCBS = general conspiracy belief scale, GCBS-G = GCBS – general factor, GCBS-UFO = GCBS – UFO related, OC = ontological confusion, PBS = paranormal belief scale (reduced), RB = religious beliefs.

In the first stage of our analysis, we looked at the correlations between the receptivity and sharing of bullshit statements, mundane statements, and motivational quotes and the variables related to

cognitive abilities, analytic thinking, and epistemically suspect beliefs. The results are presented in Table 2. The correlations reveal similar patterns between the relationships to those observed in the Pennycook et al. (2015) study. Bullshit reception correlated positively with cognitive variables, epistemically suspect beliefs, and religious beliefs. The variables related to the motivational and mundane statements correlated mainly with cognitive reflection and intelligence, but in some cases, they also related to several epistemically suspect beliefs, such as belief in complementary and alternative medicine and religious beliefs.

Table 2. Correlations between all variables included in the study.

	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.	13.	14.	15.	16.	17.	18.
1. age	1																	
2. gender	-.019	1																
3. BSR	-.224	.172	1															
4. BSS	.255	.120	-.541	1														
5. MQR	.095	.289	.261	.670	1													
6. MSR	.295	.233	.273	.067	.318	1												
7. SBS	-.076	.231	.480	-.171	.227	.313	1											
8. SMQ	.096	.327	.312	.263	.577	.311	.555	1										
9. SMS	.299	.066	.186	-.002	.161	.575	.482	.495	1									
10. BCAM	.049	.131	.193	.041	.217	.266	.085	.178	.120	1								
11. UCAM	.060	.309	.101	.074	.174	.107	.117	.224	.101	.438	1							
12. GCBS	-.145	.177	.292	-.170	.063	.019	.074	.105	-.041	.312	.292	1						
13. GCBS-G	-.139	.191	.260	-.116	.095	.030	.058	.124	-.066	.275	.305	.972	1					
14. GCBS-UFO	-.105	.060	.276	-.270	-.066	-.024	.095	.002	.056	.300	.133	.678	.490	1				
15. OC	-.160	-.011	.272	-.166	.050	.103	.242	-.005	.112	.039	.007	.199	.199	.116	1			
16. PBS	-.041	.355	.281	-.063	.176	.076	.144	.166	.063	.450	.382	.553	.493	.518	.146	1		
17. RB	-.097	.224	.214	-.053	.128	.068	.312	.281	.183	-.025	-.041	-.019	.023	-.144	.143	.120	1	
18. CRT	.134	-.289	-.214	.023	-.162	-.252	-.242	-.322	-.231	-.185	-.174	-.106	-.106	-.063	-.085	-.233	-.150	1
19. VMT	-.065	-.237	-.187	-.064	-.239	-.210	-.243	-.218	-.192	-.137	-.133	-.081	-.081	-.028	-.151	-.156	-.119	.535

Notes. $N = 121$. All correlations over .179 are significant at $p < .05$, all correlations over .234 are significant at $p < .01$, and all correlations over .296 are significant at $p < .001$ level. (two-tailed). BSR = bullshit receptivity, BSS = bullshit sensitivity, MQR = motivational quote receptivity, MSR = mundane statement receptivity, SBS = sharing bullshit, SMQ = sharing motivational quotes, SMS = sharing mundane statements, BCAM = belief in complementary and alternative medicine, UCAM = use of complementary and alternative medicine, GCBS = general conspiracy belief scale, GCBS-G = GCBS – general factor, GCBS-UFO = GCBS – UFO related, OC = ontological confusion, PBS = paranormal belief scale (reduced), RB = religious beliefs, CRT = cognitive reflection test, VMT = Vienna matrix test. Gender was coded as: 1 = male, 2 = female.

Next, we examined the correlations between the participant's demographic characteristics, profundity ratings, and sharing propensities for bullshit, mundane statements, and motivational quotes. The results are presented in Table 2. As can be seen from the table, the profundity ratings for each scale were strongly correlated with the propensity to share the items on the respective scale. Also, sharing propensities for bullshit, mundane statements, and motivational quotes were strongly intercorrelated. Overall, women rated the motivational and mundane statements as more profound and reported a greater willingness to share bullshit and motivational quotes, but age played a consistent role only in the case of the mundane statements, which older participants rated as more profound and reported a greater willingness to share them.

Then, we examined the potential predictors of bullshit receptivity, bullshit sensitivity, and bullshit sharing propensity. We used hierarchical regression analyses and entered the predictors in three stages. In the first stage, the participants' sample and demographic variables (age and gender) were entered, because in the correlational analysis age and gender were significantly related to some of the outcome variables and we wanted to control for the effect of these variables at later stages of the regression. In the second stage, we included predictors related to analytic thinking and cognitive abilities (CRT and VMT), because these variables are regarded as individual predictors in the thinking and reasoning literature. Finally, in the third stage, we entered all the variables relating to epistemically suspect beliefs – belief in and use of alternative medicine (BCAM, UCAM); paranormal beliefs (PBS); ontological confusion (OC); religious beliefs (RF); and belief in conspiracies (GCBS-G, GCBS-UFO). This was to assess whether they predicted bullshit receptivity, sensitivity, and sharing over and above the demographic characteristics and individual difference measures.

In the first two steps of the analysis on the predictors of bullshit receptivity (Table 3), age emerged as a significant predictor, with older participants judging bullshit statements to be less profound. However, once the predictors pertaining to the epistemically suspect beliefs had been entered in the last step of the regression, age no longer had a significant effect. Interestingly, neither intelligence nor analytic thinking disposition, as measured by the CRT, predicted receptivity to bullshit statements. However, ontological confusions, religious beliefs, and UFO conspiracy beliefs

were the strongest predictors of profundity ratings, although the results pertaining to these variables were only marginally significant.

Table 3. Summary of Hierarchical Regression Analysis for variables predicting Bullshit receptivity

Variable	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	β
Constant	2.674	.490		3.122	.548		2.033	.608	
Sample	.096	.170	.074	.138	.170	.107	.023	.169	.018
Gender	.323	.186	.218†	.271	.186	.183	.107	.193	.072
Age	-.019	.009	-.197*	-.018	.009	-.185†	-.014	.009	-.148
IQ				-.018	.015	-.133	-.012	.014	-.085
CRT				-.025	.030	-.089	-.015	.029	-.055
BCAM							.070	.076	.093
UCAM							-.018	.124	-.015
PBS							.017	.093	.021
OC							.170	.092	.166†
RF							.120	.064	.170†
GCBS-G							.035	.072	.051
GCBS-UFO							.104	.060	.192†
R ² (adj. R ²)	.081 (.057)			.115 (.077)			.243 (.159)		
F for change in R ²	3.424*			2.257			2.603*		

Notes. $N = 121$. The table shows the unstandardized regression coefficients (b) and corresponding standard errors (SE) as well as the standardized regression coefficients (β). Significant predictors appear in bold. Sample was coded as: 0 = Slovak, 1 = Romanian. Gender was coded as: 1 = male, 2 = female. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. † $p < .10$

The hierarchical regression analysis with bullshit sensitivity as the dependent variable (Table 4) similarly showed that, although age was a (marginally) significant predictor, it did not predict sensitivity once the epistemically suspect beliefs had been entered into the regression. As was the case in the previous analysis, neither of the cognitive factors entered during the second step of the regression were significant predictors of bullshit sensitivity. However, UFO conspiracy beliefs once again emerged as a predictor of sensitivity to the bullshit statements.

Table 4. Summary of Hierarchical Regression Analysis for variables predicting Bullshit sensitivity

Variable	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	β
Constant	.834	.628		.888	.714		1.515	.817	
Sample	-	.218	-.254†	-	.221	-.260†	-.350	.227	-.208
	.426			.437					
Gender	-	.239	-.048	-	.243	-.041	-.010	.260	-.005
	.092			.079					
Age	.022	.012	.178†	.021	.012	.165†	.015	.013	.121
IQ				-	.019	-.038	-.010	.019	-.057
				.007					
CRT				.025	.039	.070	.027	.039	.075
BCAM							.088	.102	.089
UCAM							.043	.167	.028
PBS							.040	.125	.040
OC							-	.124	-.078
							.104		
RF							-.088	.086	-.095
GCBS-G							-.005	.097	-.0006
GCBS-UFO							-.204	.080	-.290*
R ² (adj. R ²)	.109 (.087)			.113 (.074)			.193 (.103)		
F for change in R ²	4.792**			0.206			1.536		

Notes. $N = 121$. Table shows unstandardized regression coefficients (*b*) and corresponding standard errors (SE) as well as standardized regression coefficients (β). Significant predictors appear in bold. Sample was coded as: 0 = Slovak, 1 = Romanian. Gender was coded as: 1 = male, 2 = female. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. † $p < .10$

Finally, the results of the regression analysis in which the dependent variable was bullshit sharing propensity were similar to the results of the previous two regressions (Table 5). Intelligence and cognitive reflection were again not significant predictors. However, at the third stage of the analysis, both ontological confusions and religious beliefs significantly predicted willingness to share bullshit statements. Notably, women were more willing to share bullshit statements than men; however, once epistemically suspect beliefs had been entered into the regression, gender was no longer a significant predictor.

Table 5. Summary of Hierarchical Regression Analysis for variables predicting Bullshit sharing

Variable	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	β
Constant	.967	.601		1.620	.666		.620	.749	
Sample	.163	.209	.104	.226	.206	.144	.098	.208	.063
Gender	.538	.228	.300*	.461	.226	.257*	.304	.238	.169
Age	-.005	.011	-.040	-.003	.012	-	.000	.012	.000
						.024			
IQ				-.027	.018	-.158	-.019	.017	-.112
CRT				-.038	.036	-.113	-.031	.036	-.093
BCAM							.007	.094	.008
UCAM							.125	.153	.085
PBS							-.068	.114	-.072
OC								.113	.182*
							.227		
RF							.229	.079	
									.267**
GCBS-G							-.086	.089	-.104
GCBS-UFO							.107	.074	.163
R ² (adj. R ²)	.063 (.039)			.114 (.076)			.221 (.134)		
F for change in R ²	2.633 †			3.327 *			2.099 *		

Notes. $N = 121$. Table shows unstandardized regression coefficients (b) and their corresponding standard errors (SE) as well as standardized regression coefficients (β). Significant predictors appear in bold. Sample was coded as: 0 = Slovak, 1 = Romanian. Gender was coded as: 1 = male, 2 = female. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. † $p < .10$

In sum, although there were several differences in the results of the regressions pertaining to bullshit receptivity, sensitivity, and sharing, some general patterns emerged. While there were weak-to-moderate relationships between gender and age and the aforementioned variables, with women being a little more receptive and willing to share the bullshit statements than men, and older participants being slightly less receptive and more sensitive to bullshit than the younger participants, neither of these variables significantly predicted the outcomes once the epistemically suspect beliefs had been entered into the equation. Importantly, across all three analyses neither intelligence nor analytic thinking disposition predicted bullshit receptivity, sensitivity, or sharing. However, certain

epistemically suspect beliefs consistently emerged as predictors of the bullshit related variables. Specifically, UFO conspiracy beliefs, religious beliefs, and ontological confusions were the strongest and the only predictors of bullshit receptivity, sensitivity, and sharing. While the extent to which these variables predicted three bullshit related outcomes differed, the three epistemically suspect beliefs were the most consistent predictors in our analyses. Thus, our results support the view that demographic and general cognitive factors play a small role in predicting bullshit related variables; however, bullshit receptivity, sensitivity, and sharing may be closely related to several dimensions of epistemically suspect beliefs.

Discussion

Our main aim was to extend the findings related to bullshit receptivity and tendency to belief in other epistemically suspect beliefs, such as paranormal beliefs, conspiracy theories, and complementary and alternative medicine, to (1) a different cultural context and (2) to propensity to share the bullshit. The data collected is consistent with the data in Pennycook et al. (2015) on the variables relating to belief (e.g., paranormal belief, alternative medicine, conspiracy ideation) and ontological confusion. Using measures that were conceptually the same as in the original study, we found correlations similar to those reported by Pennycook et al. (2015), at least in relation to the psychological variables common to both studies. All these significant relationships were weaker than those reported by Pennycook et al. (2015), but in the expected direction.

Some differences in the strength of the relationships could have been caused by slight modifications to the methods used. For example, in the original study stronger relationships were observed with verbal intelligence than with Raven's matrices, which could explain the weaker correlation between bullshit receptivity and intelligence in our study, as the VMT is based on Raven's matrices and does not measure verbal intelligence. We wanted to include a measure of verbal intelligence in this study precisely because we thought it more relevant to bullshit receptivity (more verbally competent people should be better able to see the nonsense in vaguely and obscurely formulated sentences), but we were unable to find a standardized measure of verbal intelligence that

would be exactly the same in both countries. On the other hand, we found a stronger correlation between bullshit receptivity and conspiracy ideation, which was measured using the same instrument as in the original study and we too observed a negative relationship between bullshit receptivity and cognitive reflection.

Based on the generally similar result, we conclude that the results concerning bullshit receptivity are generalizable at least to adolescent and college samples in Eastern European countries. Our results suggest that young people are relatively open to vague sounding and impression inducing statements resembling New Age spirituality and that they do not differ much from their peers in Western countries. This may be due to globalisation, as manifest in buzzwords taken from international scientific sources (frequency, vibrations, quantum energy, phenomena, self-actualisation, intuition, bioelectricity, etc.). Despite differences between languages, these words probably have the same impression inducing connotations in all languages that assimilate new words from science and culture. It would be interesting, then, to examine differences in bullshit receptivity using statements with a non-spiritual content, for example relating to health and politics.

We want to draw attention to two new findings relating to issues not tested in the original study. The first concerns the inclusion of a measure of bullshit sharing, and the second relates to the examination of independent individual predictors of bullshit receptivity, sensitivity, and sharing using regression analyses.

Propensity to share pseudo-profound bullshit should indirectly reflect judgements of profundity, and we expected people would want to share ideas they found inspiring or thought worth spreading, that is, ideas that are more profound. As our results showed, the correlations with belief in complementary and alternative medicine, conspiracy theories, and paranormal beliefs disappeared; sharing bullshit was positively related only to ontological confusion and religious beliefs (more strongly to the latter). Sharing motivational quotes was related only to use of complementary and alternative medicine and religious beliefs; sharing mundane statements was not related to epistemically suspect beliefs, only to religious beliefs. Interestingly, the negative correlations between sharing bullshit, motivational quotes, and mundane statements and cognitive reflection and intelligence remained significant and were more pronounced (compared with the profundity ratings).

This can be interpreted as indicating that when people have a personal stake, they are more cautious about spreading bullshit. Alternatively, people may not generally be very willing to share their personal attitudes toward the transcendental realm on social media networks, even when finding these statements to be profound. The correlations between judging various types of statements (bullshit, motivational quotes, mundane statements) as profound and willingness to share them revealed that people who are more receptive to bullshit are generally more receptive to motivational quotes and see more profundity in mundane statements as well, and this is in turn related to a greater willingness to share all these kinds of statements. This suggests that some people exhibit a response bias toward higher profundity ratings. These results are similar to those obtained by Pennycook and Rand (2017). They examined the sharing of fake news, while we examined the sharing of pseudo-profound bullshit. In both studies the results showed that receptivity to bullshit was connected with more uncritical sharing – regardless of whether it was fake news and news in general that was being shared or motivational, mundane, or nonsense quotes of an unknown origin. This could reflect a general propensity to see various kinds of content (mundane, deep, or nonsensical) as more informative and profound and this general lack of bullshit sensitivity results in a more uncritical sharing of everything.

However, willingness to share bullshit was related to higher ontological confusion (the tendency to understand metaphorical expressions literally) and religious belief on one hand, and lower cognitive reflection and intelligence on the other. Interestingly, cognitive reflection and intelligence not only related to lower bullshit receptivity, but also to giving generally lower profundity ratings to motivational quotes and mundane statements, as well as to a weaker general willingness to indiscriminately share these kinds of statements on social media. This suggests that, at least in our samples, analytic thinking may guard against bullshit receptivity (response bias towards assuming profundity) but not against bullshit sensitivity per se.

The second novel element in our study was using regression analysis to examine how various demographic, cognitive, and epistemic belief variables predicted bullshit receptivity, bullshit sensitivity, and the propensity to share bullshit. Only age appeared to be a consistent predictor in all three dependent variables, with older participants being better at detecting bullshit. This might reflect

the development of more rational thinking during the transition from adolescence to young adulthood (Albert & Steinberg, 2011). Cognitive variables, such as intelligence and cognitive reflection, were not significant predictors, while ontological confusions and religious beliefs tended to predict bullshit receptivity (only marginally) and bullshit sharing (significantly). The fact that religious beliefs acted as a predictor can be partially attributed to the spiritual nature of the bullshit statements used, which were mostly based on source material taken from New Age beliefs or imitations thereof. Although epistemically suspect beliefs, such as a belief in paranormal, complementary, and alternative medicine, and conspiracies, correlated significantly with bullshit receptivity, they were not significant predictors. It may be that, in fact, bullshit receptivity predicts the holding of various epistemically suspect beliefs, or that both bullshit receptivity and epistemically suspect beliefs can be predicted by some other factor. The latter explanation is favoured by Lindeman and Aarnio (2007), who argue that one important predictor of various pseudoscientific beliefs is a core misconception about the nature of reality (ontological confusion). This confusion manifests itself in the inability to distinguish factual statements from metaphorical ones. In pseudo-profound statements falsehoods are often disguised through the (incorrect and nonsensical) use of scientific terms, which often leads to connections being drawn between everyday psychological phenomena and unrelated terms taken from physics. Ontological confusion manifests itself in the incorrect and inappropriate attribution of psychological, biological, or physical explanations of various phenomena. The ontologically confused person may also be more susceptible to becoming confused by bullshit, as it also combines unrelated phenomena to create a semblance of meaning.

Similar results have been reported by other researchers (Lobato, Mendoza, Sims, & Chin, 2014), who have found that ontological confusion acts as a predictor of various intercorrelated epistemically suspect beliefs. The propensity for believing and sharing pseudo-profound bullshit correlates with other epistemically suspect beliefs and can be considered an epistemically suspect belief itself.

It is possible that we did not find individual predictors to contribute significantly to the model because the majority were mutually correlated. As most of the epistemically suspect belief variables were related to each other, albeit modestly, this would explain why entering them into the regression together led to an increase in the predictive power of the model, even though most of them did not

emerge as significant predictors. While this may have affected the regression coefficients of individual predictors, the results regarding the predictive power of the model should still hold. Nonetheless, we still found a pattern in relation to age, religious beliefs, and ontological confusion in particular.

Limitations and Further research

Researchers should be wary of differences in conspiracy beliefs between cultures or nations. The original research (Pennycook et al., 2015) was conducted on undergraduate students and on Amazon Mechanical Turk American-only participants. Given the different historical backgrounds, the landscape of conspiracy theories differs considerably among populations. What is of interest to the conspiracy theorist in the United States may not be relevant to the conspiracy theorist in Europe and vice versa. There are some conspiracy theories that are probably shared globally (e.g., 9/11 or the moon landing hoax), but many are relevant only to certain regions or cultures (e.g., it is unlikely that the conspiracy theorist from the US will be concerned about conspiracy theories relating to the European Union or the death of Princess Diana, etc.). The same might be true of the other measures we used, or the same paranormal beliefs or pseudoscientific remedies might be relevant in different countries.

Time may also play a role. Some previously popular epistemically suspect beliefs are now dated, such as phrenology (Finger, 2005), while other beliefs have emerged only relatively recently, such as the idea that vaccines cause autism (Baker, 2008).

Nevertheless, we succeeded in building upon a framework that had been established in the original studies on pseudo-profound bullshit, and we expect that future research will involve the use of more controlled materials and perhaps investigate other domains, such as bullshit in health, politics, advertising, or even academia. As was discussed in the introduction, bullshit can be defined variously and used in domains other than the quasi-spiritual one. We are also seeing different types of bullshit. Some politicians spout ill-founded claims with no regard for the truth and various fraudulent websites give pretend medical advice that has the potential to mislead people and cause harm. Future research could also focus on a taxonomy of bullshit and on receptivity/sensitivity to authentic cases of bullshit (although the Bullshit Receptivity Scale included some authentic cases of bullshit taken from Chopra's

Twitter, they were all of the same spiritual/pseudoscientific kind). Other types of bullshit could be predicted by a different set of predictors. The perceived veracity of bullshit statements may also be influenced by other information, including authorship or visual content paired with bullshit statements. The perceived veracity or profundity of bullshit statements is not based on evidence, it usually relates to a concept of “truthiness” in which the truth of a statement is judged by “gut feeling” and this feeling can be manipulated by pairing statements with relevant or irrelevant photos or by giving authors pseudonyms that are easily pronounced (Newman et al., 2014, 2015). Further research could examine the effect of this kind of paired information on the perceived profundity or veracity of bullshit statements or on willingness to share them.

Conclusion

In this paper we examined whether bullshit receptivity was related to belief in other epistemically suspect beliefs, such as paranormal beliefs, conspiracy theories, and complementary and alternative medicine and lower cognitive abilities using a sample from two Eastern European countries. Moreover, we examined whether this relationship was more pronounced in bullshit sharing. The results indicated that the new measure we used – bullshit sharing on social media – correlated with profundity ratings of bullshit. Generally, we found that the more profound a given statement was rated to be (regardless of whether it was bullshit, a motivational quote, or a mundane statement), the more likely it was to be shared. Moreover, we found that propensity for sharing bullshit was predicted by ontological confusion and religious beliefs. In other words, the more literally people understood metaphorical statements and the more religious they were, the more prone they were to sharing not only bullshit but also various motivational and mundane statements on social media.

Our results imply that people who judge a wider spectrum of statements as profound tend to be more willing to share indiscriminate content on social media, and thus (unknowingly) spread bullshit further. This suggests that the best way to stop the spread of nonsense on social media and in our daily lives is to improve both people’s ability to inhibit the first thought that comes into their mind (cognitive reflection) and the cognitive capacity to think more about the items we encounter. However,

because not all people are willing or able to spend more time contemplating the content they choose to share on social media, practical interventions should focus on cueing analytic thinking and highlighting the consequences of spreading untruthful and often harmful information.

References

- Albert, D., & Steinberg, L. (2011). Judgment and decision making in adolescence. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 21(1), 211–224. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1532-7795.2010.00724.x>
- Baker, J. P. (2008). Mercury, vaccines, and autism. *American Journal of Public Health*, 98(2), 244–253. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2007.113159>
- Ballová Mikušková, E. (2017). Conspiracy beliefs in future teachers. *Current Psychology*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-017-9561-4>
- Bazarova, N. N., Taft, J. G., Choi, Y. H., & Cosley, D. (2013). Managing impressions and relationships on Facebook. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 32(2), 121–141. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261927X12456384>
- Black, M. (1982). The prevalence of humbug. *Philosophic Exchange*, 13(1). Retrieved from http://digitalcommons.brockport.edu/phil_ex/vol13/iss1/4
- Bond, C. F., & DePaulo, B. M. (2006). Accuracy of deception judgments. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 10(3), 214–234. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327957pspr1003_2
- Brotherton, R., French, C. C., & Pickering, A. D. (2013). Measuring belief in conspiracy theories: the generic conspiracist beliefs scale. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4(May), 279. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00279>
- Bruder, M., Haffke, P., Neave, N., Nouripannah, N., & Imhoff, R. (2013). Measuring individual differences in generic beliefs in conspiracy theories across cultures: conspiracy mentality questionnaire. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4(April), 225. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00225>
- Buekens, F., & Boundry, M. (2015). The dark side of the loon. Explaining the temptations of obscurantism. *Theoria*, 81(2), 126–142. <https://doi.org/10.1111/theo.12047>
- Dalton, C. (2016). Bullshit for you; transcendence for me. A commentary on “ On the reception and detection of pseudo-profound bullshit .” *Judgment and Decision Making*, 11(1), 121–122.

- Deppe, K. D., Gonzalez, F. J., Neiman, J. L., Jacobs, C., Pahlke, J., & Smith, K. B. (2015). Reflective liberals and intuitive conservatives : A look at the Cognitive Reflection Test and ideology, *10*(4), 314–331.
- Finger, S. (2005). *Minds Behind the Brain*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195181821.001.0001>
- Frankfurt, H. G. (2005). *On Bullshit*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10584600701641920>
- Frederick, S. (2005). Cognitive reflection and decision making. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, *19*(4), 25–42. <https://doi.org/10.1257/089533005775196732>
- Henrich, J., Heine, S. J., & Norenzayan, A. (2010). The weirdest people in the world? *The Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, *33*, 61-83; discussion 83-135. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X0999152X>
- Klose, J., Černochová, D., & Král, P. (2002). *Vídeňský maticový test*. Praha: Testcentrum.
- Lewandowsky, S., Ecker, U. K. H., & Cook, J. (2017). Beyond misinformation: Understanding and coping with the “Post-Truth” Era. *Journal of Applied Research in Memory and Cognition*, *6*(4), 353–369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JARMAC.2017.07.008>
- Lindeman, M. (2011). Biases in intuitive reasoning and belief in complementary and alternative medicine. *Psychology & Health*, *26*(3), 371–382. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08870440903440707>
- Lindeman, M., & Aarnio, K. (2007). Superstitious, magical, and paranormal beliefs: An integrative model. *Journal of Research in Personality*, *41*(4), 731–744.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2006.06.009>
- Lobato, E., Mendoza, J., Sims, V., & Chin, M. (2014). Examining the relationship between conspiracy theories , paranormal beliefs , and pseudoscience acceptance among a university population. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, *28*(5), 617–625. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.3042>
- Meibauer, J. (2016). Aspects of a theory of bullshit, *1*, 68–91. <https://doi.org/10.1075/pc.23.1.04mei>
- Newman, E. J., Garry, M., Unkelbach, C., Bernstein, D. M., Stephen Lindsay, D., & Nash, R. A. (2015). Truthiness and falsiness of trivia claims depend on judgmental contexts. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning Memory and Cognition*, *41*(5), 1337–1348.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/xlm0000099>

- Newman, E. J., Sanson, M., Miller, E. K., Quigley-McBride, A., Foster, J. L., Bernstein, D. M., & Garry, M. (2014). People with easier to pronounce names promote truthiness of claims. *PLoS ONE*, *9*(2). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0088671>
- Oppenheimer, D. M. (2006). Consequences of erudite vernacular utilized irrespective of necessity: Problems with using long words needlessly. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, *20*(2), 139–156. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.1178>
- Pennycook, G., Cheyne, J. A., Barr, N., Koehler, D. J., & Fugelsang, J. A. (2015). On the reception and detection of pseudo-profound bullshit. *Judgment and Decision Making*, *10*(6), 549–563.
- Pennycook, G., Cheyne, J. A., Barr, N., Koehler, D. J., & Fugelsang, J. A. (2016). It's still bullshit: Reply to Dalton (2016). *Judgment and Decision Making*, *11*(1), 123–125.
- Pennycook, G., & Rand, D. G. (2017). Who falls for fake news? The roles of analytic thinking, motivated reasoning, political ideology, and bullshit receptivity. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3023545>
- Pfattheicher, S., & Schindler, S. (2016). Misperceiving bullshit as profound is associated with favorable views of Cruz, Rubio, Trump and conservatism. *PLoS ONE*, *11*(4), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0153419>
- Plante, T. G. (2010). The Santa Clara strength of religious faith questionnaire: Assessing faith engagement in a brief and nondenominational manner. *Religions*, *1*(1), 3–8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel1010003>
- Pollack, D. (2003). Religiousness inside and outside the church in selected post-Communist countries of Central and Eastern Europe. *Social Compass*, *50*(3), 321–334. Retrieved from www.sagepublications.com
- Postman, N. (1969). Bullshit and the art of crap detection, 1–3.
- Sarkissian, A. (2009). Religious reestablishment in post-communist polities. *Journal of Church and State*, *51*(3), 472–501. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcs/csp096>
- Sterling, J., Jost, J. T., & Pennycook, G. (2016). Are neoliberals more susceptible to bullshit? *Judgment and Decision Making*, *11*(4), 352–360. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>

- Talhelm, T., Haidt, J., Oishi, S., Zhang, X., Miao, F. F., & Chen, S. (2015). Liberals think more analytically (more 'Weird') than Conservatives. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, *41*(2), 250–267. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2111700>
- Tobacyk, J. J. (2004). A Revised Paranormal Belief Scale. *International Journal of Transpersonal Studies*, *23*(1), 94–98. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t14015-000>
- Wakeham, J. (2017). Bullshit as a problem of social epistemology. *Sociological Theory*, *35*(1), 15–38. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0735275117692835>